

ACINO / D5.1

Definition of test-bed scenarios and use-cases

Dissemination level	PU
Version	1
Due date	31/01/2017
Version date	16/03/2017

This project is funded
by the European Union

Document information

Authors

Victor Lopez, Miguel Angel Carnero, Oscar Gonzalez de Dios – TID

Ćiril Rožić, Dimitrios Klonidis – AIT

Mohit Chamanian, Thomas Szyrkowiec – ADVA

Federico Pederzoli, Michele Santuari, Domenico Siracusa – CREATE-NET

Stéphane Junique, Pontus Sköldström – ACREO

Ori Gerstel, Yona Shikhmanter – SEDONA

Editor

Victor Lopez – TID

Project funding

645127 — ACINO — H2020-ICT-2014

Legal Disclaimer

The information in this document is provided 'as is', and no guarantee or warranty is given that the information is fit for any particular purpose. The above referenced consortium members shall have no liability for damages of any kind including without limitation direct, special, indirect, or consequential damages that may result from the use of these materials subject to any liability which is mandatory due to applicable law.

Table of contents

Document information	ii
Table of contents	iii
List of tables	v
Summary	7
1 Introduction	8
2 Preliminary tests	9
2.1 Orchestrator demonstration	9
2.2 Policy-based Restoration in IP/Optical Transport Networks	12
2.3 DISMI preliminary demonstration	14
3 Description of the preliminary testbed	17
3.1 Data Communication Network	17
3.2 Physical setup	18
3.3 Emulated environment	22
4 Definition of the use case validation	24
4.1 Application-Centric Intent-based IP-Optical Orchestration	24
4.2 Enabling dynamic services using the intent interface	24
4.3 Application aware In-flight Encryption	27
4.4 Virtual CDN (vCDN) adaptation	27
4.5 In-operation network planning	29
5 Validation of the ACINO Framework	32
5.1 Scope	32
5.2 Lab Tests	32
5.3 Optical Layer tests	32

5.4 IP Layer tests	34
5.5 Multi-layer Orchestrator	34
6 Conclusions	37
Annex 1 OpenVPN configuration procedure	38
Annex 2 NAT configuration with IPtables to allow direct access to the internal setup	46
Annex 3 Juniper vMX configuration procedure	47
Annex 4 Juniper logical systems configuration procedure	55
Annex 5 In-flight encryption with ADVA ConnectGuard	56
References	57

List of figures

Figure 2.1: High level testbed overview.	9
Figure 2.2: Network Testbed Configuration.	10
Figure 2.3: First request to the ACINO orchestrator.	10
Figure 2.4: Network Testbed Configuration after first request.....	11
Figure 2.5: Second request to the ACINO orchestrator.	11
Figure 2.6: Network Testbed Configuration after second request.....	12
Figure 2.7: High level testbed overview.	13
Figure 2.8: Combined sequence diagrams for the optical and IP restoration scenarios.	13
Figure 2.9: Information model to construct an Intent: primitives and how they connect to form a grammar.	14
Figure 2.10: The command-line interface of the DISMI client, during a demonstration.	16
Figure 3.1: Illustration of the VPN connection with the Telefonica lab.	18
Figure 3.2: Illustration of the physical setup.	19
Figure 3.3: Optical ring topology.	20
Figure 3.4: Generic Network Element Layout.	21
Figure 3.5: NE with fiber cut emulation.	22
Figure 3.6: Illustration of the emulated setup.....	22
Figure 4.1 : Network used to demonstrate requesting dynamic services using the intent interface.....	25
Figure 4.2: Network in which a single network service, depicted by the blue sinusoidal curves, has been set up. The service fulfils the bandwidth requirement, but the latency is high.	26
Figure 4.3: Network which a two network service have been set up: the blue sinusoidal curves depict the high-bandwidth service, and the green sinusoidal curves depict the low-latency service.....	26
Figure 4.4: Experimental setup to demonstrate in-flight encryption.	27
Figure 4.5: vCDN transfer to the point with lower latency.	28
Figure 4.6: vCDN transfers to vCDN2 the content.....	28
Figure 4.7: Initial network for in-operation planning.	29
Figure 4.8: a) New IP link established and App1 is accommodated; b) App2 is accommodated in the IP layer.	30
Figure 4.9: App2 is moved and then App3 is accommodated in the IP.	30
Figure 4.10: a) a lightpath from A to B is created and then App3 is accommodated in the IP; b) lightpaths (A,C) and (C,B) are created, then App4 is moved to IP path (A,C,B), and finally App5 is accommodated in the IP.	31

List of tables

Table 2.1 : RESTFul HTTP API with methods and routes. 15

Summary

This document describes the test-bed set-up which will be used for the experimental validation and the mechanism to demonstrate the use-cases defined in WP2 on this set-up. The document also contains preliminary tests that help the project validate initial prototypes of the ACINO orchestrator on a real setup. Finally, the deliverable provides the main functional tests to validate the ACINO orchestrator's and controller's requirements.

The deliverable starts with presenting three preliminary tests: (1) demonstration of the orchestrator with the primary objective to test the interaction with the physical set-up, (2) demonstration of differentiated network restoration based on the policy requested by the client application and (3) demonstration of the DISMI intent interface.

The test-bed description presents an overview of the Data Communication Network (DCN) that is used to interconnect partner sites, the physical and the emulated test-beds. The physical testbed comprises three Juniper routers, three ADVA nodes, and VMs to control the network devices. The consortium also has access to an emulated environment which enables functional tests on a larger set-up.

The definition of the use case validation covers the setup to demonstrate 1) service differentiation based on intents, 2) enabling of dynamic services using the intent interface, 3) encrypted application delivery, 4) vCDN adaptation and 5) in-operation network planning.

Finally, the document contains functional test cases to validate the requirements on the IP and optical controllers, as well as the ACINO orchestrator. The functional tests cover the provisioning, topology, monitoring and path computation capabilities of the IP, optical controllers and orchestrator (including DISMI and NetRap). The document also provides initial performance parameters for some of these functional tests.

1 Introduction

The present document has the aim of informing about the project's activities performed during the last year regarding the demonstration of the ACINO concepts. The tasks within WP5 are in charge of the validation activities of the ACINO architecture. The activity reported here is focused on devising experimental scenarios to validate the proposed design and demonstrate the capabilities of ACINO for use in current and future network applications.

This document starts with a section "Preliminary tests" to show the initial attempts to control the commercial IP/optical infrastructure of the project. These tests help the consortium to validate initial ideas in real experiments. The tests are done to demonstrate the capacity of the consortium to interact with the physical set-up. The section also includes the first demonstration of the control solution for transport networks, based on the client policy for an IP/Optical SDN. Finally, the Dynamic Intent-driven Service Management Interface, or DISMI, demonstration.

The next sections present the definition of the testbed and the preliminary experiments for the ACINO prototype validation, respectively. Moreover, this document reports on the experimentation framework including the physical and logical definition to test according the use cases and challenges defined in WP2. The testbed definition is an initial framework, capable of being reconfigured as required in order to create a desired use case and measure the ACINO's capabilities and performance. The physical testbed limitations are completed with the emulated environment to carry out tests without the physical limitations.

Finally, the work done in the WP5 was to define functional tests to validate the requirements of the controllers and orchestrator defined, developed and tested in the consortium.

2 Preliminary tests

This section presents the preliminary tests performed by the consortium. The tests outlined here are designed to demonstrate 1) the capability of the ACINO architecture to interact with the physical setup, 2) application differentiation via the use of intents in ONOS, and 3) the DISMI interface that can be used to define application specific intents.

2.1 Orchestrator demonstration

The objective of this test was to demonstrate the capability to interact with the physical set-up deployed at Telefonica premises. It was already presented at the Y1 review meeting.

The initial implementation of the orchestrator extends ONOS and contains three modules:

- PROXY REST Provider. This module facilitates the representation of multiple devices in ONOS while communicating with a single SDN Controller (in this case the Optical Hypervisor)
- NETCONF Juniper Driver. This module supports the configuration of Juniper routers using NETCONF.
- COP Driver. This module enables interaction with the Optical Network controller (Optical Hypervisor) using the Control Orchestration Protocol (COP) defined at EU funded project, STRAUSS project [1].

The high-level testbed overview is depicted in Figure 2.1.

Figure 2.1: High level testbed overview.

The testbed setup, as presented in Figure 2.2, consists of 3 Juniper MX240 routers (J1, J2, J3) connected via multiple 1GBE and 10GBE interfaces to 3 ADVA FSP3000 R7 WDM nodes (A1, A2, A3). The WDM nodes have the same configuration with directionless add/drop capabilities and are interconnected with each other in a ring configuration. The initial configuration of the set-up is presented in Figure 2.2. It contains the loopback IP for each router as well as an initial IP address for the interfaces involved in the test.

Figure 2.2: Network Testbed Configuration.

A first request is sent to the ACINO orchestrator. This request wants to connect J1/lo0.2 to J2/lo0.2 and vice versa (connect J2/lo0.2 to J1/lo0.2). For illustrative purpose, it is shown in Figure 2.3.

Figure 2.3: First request to the ACINO orchestrator.

Once the request arrives to the orchestrator, it computes the new path to connect both routers, which involves the creation of a new lightpath between ADVA 196 and 198 and configuration of routers on the routers J1 and J2. This is translated in the following operations at the south bound interfaces:

- NETCONF Juniper Driver J1 → Configure static route to reach J2 lo0.2.
- NETCONF Juniper Driver J2 → Configure static route to reach J1 lo0.2.
- Optical hypervisor → Install optical path (196/2-14 to 198/2-14).

The network testbed configuration after first request is shown in Figure 2.4.

Figure 2.4: Network Testbed Configuration after first request.

A second request is sent to the ACINO orchestrator. This request wants to connect J2/lo0.2 to J3/lo0.2 and vice versa (connect J2/lo0.2 to J3/lo0.2). The second request is shown in Figure 2.5.

Figure 2.5: Second request to the ACINO orchestrator.

The second request arrives to the orchestrator, which calculates the second path to connect both routers. This is translated in the following operations at the south bound interfaces:

- NETCONF Juniper Driver J3 → Configure static route to reach J2 lo0.2.
- NETCONF Juniper Driver J2 → Configure static route to reach J3 lo0.2.
- Optical hypervisor → Install optical path (197/2-13 to 198/2-13).

The network testbed configuration after first request is shown in Figure 2.6.

Figure 2.6: Network Testbed Configuration after second request.

2.2 Policy-based Restoration in IP/Optical Transport Networks

This experiment proposed the first demonstration of restoration on IP or optical layer, requested explicitly by the client application, using IP/Optical SDN control solutions. The policy is communicated via intents, as part of the constraints that must be satisfied for a service. The orchestrator uses these intents to identify the restoration mechanism to be employed in case of a failure. The proposed orchestration solution allows the operator to effectively utilize network resources while ensuring that the survivability constraints of requested services are met. It was presented at the NetSoft 2016 conference [2].

This work is an evolution of the demo done at the Y1 review, improving the complexity of the workflow and demonstrates the capability to process notifications from the underlying infrastructure. Figure 2.7 presents a high-level overview of the testbed, including both the hardware and the network orchestrator. The IP and optical ports are numbered, while the color code (orange, blue, green) identifies distinct wavelengths that are used on these interfaces. Therefore, a lightpath can be established between J1/1 and J2/1 (orange), J2/3 and J3/2 (green), and any pair of interfaces J1/2, J2/2 or J3/1 (blue), where Jx/y represents router Jx port y. The testbed setup provides diversity with respect to optical paths and capacity between any pair of routers.

Figure 2.7: High level testbed overview.

In the demonstration, we assume that an interconnection between an IP router and a ROADM fails, generating a port down alarm sent by both the OVC and the IP router (only J1 was configured to send port-down alarms). According to the policy specified on the installed intent, the orchestrator attempts to restore the service at the optical or the IP layer. The combined sequence diagrams are shown in Figure 2.8.

Figure 2.8: Combined sequence diagrams for the optical and IP restoration scenarios.

This demonstration highlights the capability to apply policies defined in service requests to dynamically perform restoration at the IP or optical layer after a failure occurs. The capability to dynamically evaluate and perform restoration on a per-service level is essential for the effective utilization of network resources in the next-generation transport networks.

2.3 DISMI preliminary demonstration

The Dynamic Intent-driven Service Management Interface, or DISMI, is a northbound interface of the ACINO orchestrator. The DISMI is REST-based, and uses the Intent paradigm: it exposes primitives and a grammar, which together form an information model that client *applications* can use to request network *services*. This information model, shown in Figure 2.9, allows application to request *What* they need instead of *How* to build a service.

Figure 2.9: Information model to construct an Intent: primitives and how they connect to form a grammar.

The DISMI was demonstrated during the first-year review, and has the following components:

- A REST server connected to a standalone store and processing incoming requests. The server was running in a terminal window, and incoming calls printed out the call content. The DISMI server exposed the REST interfaces shown in Table 2.1.

- A client program with a command-line interface was running in another terminal window, as depicted in Figure 2.10. It performed the following operations:
 - Connection to the REST server, and retrieval of the information model (but the information model was not parsed in the client. Instead, the information model was hard-coded).
 - Retrieval of the list of connection points
 - Building of a service containing an Intent with a Path, selectors and Constraints (see Figure 2.9)
 - Submission of the service to the server.
 - Request for the status of the submitted service

Table 2.1 : RESTful HTTP API with methods and routes.

Method	Route	Description
GET	/service	Get a list of the current services' ids
GET	/service/{id}	Gets overview of a specific service
GET	/service/{id}/{id}	Gets overview of a specific intent in a service
GET	/service/all	Gets overview of all current services
POST	/service	Create a new service
PUT	/service/{id}	Update a service
PUT	/service/{id}/{id}	Update an intent in a service
DELETE	/service/{id}	Delete a service
DELETE	/service/{id}/{id}	Delete an intent in a service
GET	/connectionpoint	Gets a list of the defined ConnectionPoints' ids
GET	/connectionpoint/{name}	Gets overview of a specific ConnectionPoint
GET	/connectionpoint/all	Gets overview of all ConnectionPoints
PUT	/connectionpoint/{name}	Update a ConnectionPoint (e.g. change name)
POST	/connectionpoint/{name}	Create a new ConnectionPoint <-> EndPoint mapping
GET	/capabilities	Gets a list of capabilities (Actions) and associated schemas' names
GET	/capabilities/{name}	Gets a schema for a particular capability

```

Version:0.0.5
Welcome to DISMI CLI
dismi>connect
URL = [http://localhost:8080]
dismi>get connectionpoints
Fetched 4 connection-points.
dismi>list connectionpoints

```

Identifier	Name
1	Brussels
2	Stockholm
3	Madrid
4	Trento

```

dismi>add service --name Connection-Bru-Sto
Staged service: Connection-Bru-Sto
dismi-service>ls
class Service {
  displayName: Connection-Bru-Sto
  intents: []
}
dismi-service>add path --from Brussels --to Stockholm

dismi-intent>ls
class Intent {
  displayName: Path from Brussels to Stockholm
  action: class Path {
    class Action {
    }
  }
  source: class Subject {
    connectionPoint: class ConnectionPoint {
      name: Brussels
      endpoints: [class IPEndPoint {
        class EndPoint {
        }
      } routerId: 1
      portId: 4
      inAddr: 10.4.144.1
    }, class EthEndPoint {
      class EndPoint {
      }
      switchId: SW01
      portId: 1
    }
  }
  }
  selectors: []
  constraints: []
}
destination: class Subject {
  connectionPoint: class ConnectionPoint {
    name: Stockholm
    endpoints: [class IPEndPoint {
      class EndPoint {
      }
    } routerId: 1
    portId: 7
    inAddr: 10.4.142.1
  }, class EthEndPoint {
    class EndPoint {
    }
    switchId: SW4
    portId: 3
  }
  }
  selectors: []
  constraints: []
}
}
selectors: []
constraints: []
}

```

Figure 2.10: The command-line interface of the DISMI client, during a demonstration.

3 Description of the preliminary testbed

This section presents an overview of the environment used to experimentally validate the ACINO implementation. The setup consists of the physical and emulated test-bed present in TID, and a Data Communication Network (DCN) connection that facilitates interconnection between the partner sites and the test-bed in TID.

3.1 Data Communication Network

The Data Communication Network (DCN) is composed of the control plane connections inside the TID premises and the VPN configuration to interconnect partner sites with this setup. For the permanent testbed we will have 3 ADVA optical nodes and 3 Juniper 240-MX routers with their own IP addressing.

The VPN connections to the partners are configured using OpenVPN. The OpenVPN server is installed in the Telefonica facilities in a VM (*vpnacino*). Once the 5 certificates and the configuration files are generated by the server, these have to be installed in the OpenVPN clients of the partners.

The following files are generated by Telefonica:

```
1./etc/openvpn/ca.crt
2./etc/openvpn/easy-rsa/keys/client1.crt
3./etc/openvpn/easy-rsa/keys/client1.key
4./etc/openvpn/easy-rsa/keys/client2.crt
5./etc/openvpn/easy-rsa/keys/client2.key
6./etc/openvpn/easy-rsa/keys/client3.crt
7./etc/openvpn/easy-rsa/keys/client3.key
8./etc/openvpn/easy-rsa/keys/client4.crt
9./etc/openvpn/easy-rsa/keys/client4.key
10./etc/openvpn/easy-rsa/keys/client5.crt
11./etc/openvpn/easy-rsa/keys/client5.key
```

For each partner, Telefonica provides 3 files. The first file (*/etc/openvpn/ca.crt*) is the same for all the partners, and is the server's certificate. The client certificates (*client*.crt*) and keys (*client*.key*) must be unique for each partner.

Five new VPN connections with ADVA, Sedona, ACREO, CREATENET and AIT are configured, meaning the OpenVPN client application is installed by each partner, and ports UDP 1194, ICMP and TCP 8080 are opened on their networks to allow the VPN traffic through the firewall.

Figure 3.1 shows the VM with the OpenVPN server and the connection with the lab using the VPNs.

Figure 3.1: Illustration of the VPN connection with the Telefonica lab.

Annex 1 describes the OpenVPN configuration in greater detail. Annex 2 describes the NAT configuration with IPtables to allow direct access to the internal setup.

3.2 Physical setup

The physical connection is showed in Figure 3.2. This configuration can change for some tests, but this is the basic configuration. The controller is installed in the VM *vpnacino* with connection to the physical setup and with the collaborators via VPNs. This control plane schemed is showed in the next section.

Figure 3.2: Illustration of the physical setup.

3.2.1 Juniper Routers

The Juniper routers located at TID premises have 20 GE ports and 2 x 10GE. The routing engine is a RE-S-1300. The pluggables (SFPs) are changed based on the tests: as an example the configuration of the MX240-1 at the time of writing this document was the following:

Item	Description
Chassis	MX240
Midplane	MX240 Backplane
FPM Board	Front Panel Display
PEM 0	PS 1.2-1.7kW; 100-240V AC in
PEM 2	PS 1.2-1.7kW; 100-240V AC in
Routing Engine 0	RE-S-1300
CB 0	MX SCB
FPC 2	DPCE 20x 1GE + 2x 10GE R
CPU	DPC PMB
PIC 0	10x 1GE (LAN)
Xcvr 0	SFP-LX10
Xcvr 1	SFP-LX10
Xcvr 2	SFP-LX10
Xcvr 3	SFP-LX10
Xcvr 9	SFP-LX10

PIC 1	10x 1GE (LAN)
Xcvr 2	SFP-LX10
Xcvr 3	SFP-EX
Xcvr 4	SFP-T
Xcvr 6	SFP-SX
Xcvr 7	SFP-SX
PIC 2	1x 10GE (LAN/WAN)
Xcvr 0	XFP-10G-LR
PIC 3	1x 10GE (LAN/WAN)
Xcvr 0	XFP-10G-LR
Fan Tray 0	MX240 Fan Tray

In order to share the same chassis for multiple experiment, the logical systems feature of Juniper is useful. With this feature, it is possible to partition a single router into multiple logical devices that perform independent routing tasks. Because logical systems perform a subset of the tasks once handled by the main router, logical systems offer an effective way to maximize the use of a single routing or switching platform. More information can be found at Juniper’s website [3].

The configuration of the logical system in the set-up is shown in the Annex 4.

3.2.2 ADVA equipment

The ADVA setup is composed by three 3 FSP3000 R7 WDM nodes (Node 1, 2, 3) and are interconnected with each other in a ring configuration (as shown in Figure 3.3).

Figure 3.3: Optical ring topology.

The WDM nodes have the same configuration with directionless add/drop capabilities. The generic network element configuration is presented in Figure 3.4. Each 8ROADM C40 is a 1x8 wavelength selectable switch, and the 4CSM module is a fixed wavelength optical channel filter. Using the switch in the configuration presented in the figure supports directionless add/drop capability as well as pass thru capabilities.

Figure 3.4: Generic Network Element Layout.

Some scenarios covered in the use cases require a network failure “event” to trigger operations like restoration. Figure 3.5 shows the configuration to emulate a fiber cut using the 4OPCM module. This module has the capability to perform variable optical power attenuation, and we use this capability to significantly increase the attenuation, thereby simulating a fiber cut between 2 ADVA nodes or on a fiber between a Juniper router and an ADVA node.

Figure 3.5: NE with fiber cut emulation.

3.3 Emulated environment

The logical view of the emulated set-up is shown in Figure 3.6.

Figure 3.6: Illustration of the emulated setup.

The orchestrator is allocated in the VM *vpnacino* as in the physical set-up, but the IP addresses of the optical controller and the Juniper Routers are different. In this way, the orchestrator uses the vMX (virtual Juniper router), instead of the MX240's and the Netphony control plane (via the ABNO controller) instead of the

ADVA physical nodes (via the Optical Hypervisor). The most relevant information of the emulated environment is:

- **Optical Emulation.** The ABNO modules and the Netphony GMPLS environment are deployed on the same machine, called simpsonsgw2. It is a server with two Intel Xeon E5-2630 2.30GHz processors (6 cores each) and 192 GB RAM. This server uses VMWare 5.0 to deploy the VMs. The installation of the VMs is public at the Netphony project wiki [4].
- **IP Emulation.** The vMX machines are deployed on another server, Server3vmt, which is a machine with two Intel Xeon E5-2697v2 2.7GHz processors (6 cores each) and 256 GB RAM with a Linux environment. The VMs are virtualized using KVM. The steps to install the virtual MX environment are shown in Annex 3.

4 Definition of the use case validation

In this section are shown how the different use cases are validated within the ACINO framework.

4.1 Application-Centric Intent-based IP-Optical Orchestration

This use case exhibits one of the core innovations proposed in ACINO, where service differentiation is demonstrated using intents that encode application requirements.

The first part of this UC, pertaining differentiated services for different applications, borrows directly from UC5.1 described in D2.2, and relies on just 3 optical Add/Drop nodes attached to as many routers, which we'll call R1, R2 and R3:

1. Suppose a demand A requires simple connectivity between R1 and R2, and a subsequent demand B connectivity between R2 and R3; the orchestrator will setup two lightpaths to serve these demands; The assumption here is that lightpath capacity is significantly larger than the bandwidth requirements of the applications.
2. A third demand, C, requires connectivity between R1 and R3, again with a required capacity that is much smaller than that of a lightpath; the orchestrator will route this demand over the existing lightpaths to save resources.
3. A fourth demand, D, also requires connectivity between R1 and R3. However, despite the fact that there is ample spare capacity on the lightpaths, the demand also encodes a strict limit on both latency and availability. If the latency limit is lower than the propagation delay on the R1-R2-R3 path, or if the historical availability of the R1-R2-R3 path is below what is required, the ACINO orchestrator will then setup a new lightpath on a direct path between R1 and R3 to serve this connection, thus showcasing differentiated service treatment.

In addition to displaying service differentiation, this UC will also be used to measure the performance of the ACINO orchestrator. Measurements will include the execution times of the various operations involved in the setup process (e.g. DISMI & Net2Plan processing, ONOS & ADVA Hypervisor configuration of devices) to give a baseline performance. Then, these times could be studied with respect to both the characteristics of the demands (presence and value of constraints, length of the resulting path) and of the underlying network (network size, resource occupation). All of these hinge on some flexibility in modelling the underlying network, and are therefore best suited for an emulated testbed.

4.2 Enabling dynamic services using the intent interface

4.2.1 Description

This use case illustrates the need for application awareness for services with multi-stream, high-performance requirements. This use case primarily demonstrates the integration of the DISMI with the orchestrator, thereby demonstrating the capability to translate application requirements into feasible network service requirements.

This use case requires the kind of network performance and features typically discussed for the upcoming 5G network standard. The scenario is that of video streaming in a stadium using drones, to transmit high-resolution video of an event such as a match (football, rugby, ...) or a concert. The network is shown in Figure 4.1 and the network service consists of two paths:

- One path enables a unidirectional connection for a high bitrate stream for the HD video from the drone to a control centre where the stream is edited, mixed with others, encoded and broadcast.
- One path allows a bidirectional connection for command and control (including low bitrate video) between the drone and the control centre, with low latency requirements but low bitrate needs.

Figure 4.1 : Network used to demonstrate requesting dynamic services using the intent interface.

4.2.2 Use case scenarios

The Intent-based interface is used to request a network service, composed of one or more intents. The three cases are shown sequentially:

- Case 1: The service request contains one intent with a single high bandwidth path which is used for both applications (streaming, drone control) the bandwidth and latency requirements of both services combined. The orchestrator is unable to provide a connection that satisfies them all, and the combined request fails.
- Case 2 (optional): The service request contains one intent with the bandwidth requirement, and lowest latency as a priority. The orchestrator sets up the network service shown in Figure 4.2: the service satisfies the bandwidth requirement, but the latency is too high for command and control. Note: This case can only be shown if support for priorities has been implemented in Net2Plan (i.e. Net2Plan calculates several routes that it can order using a priority criterion).
- Case 3: The service contains two intents: the first intent addresses the need for a high bitrate connection. The second intent requests a low latency connection for command and control. The

orchestrator sets up two separate for the two intents, using two different routes, as shown in Figure 4.3. Each route fulfils the expected requirements.

Figure 4.2: Network in which a single network service, depicted by the blue sinusoidal curves, has been set up. The service fulfils the bandwidth requirement, but the latency is high.

Figure 4.3: Network in which two network services have been set up: the blue sinusoidal curves depict the high-bandwidth service, and the green sinusoidal curves depict the low-latency service.

4.2.3 Demonstration

For each of the three (or two) cases the demonstration shows the following information:

- Request received by the DISMI REST interface (or sent by the client application)
- Key properties of the request after validation by the DISMI
- Request after compilation into ACI intents
- The properties of the resulting routes calculated by Net2Plan, shown using the Net2Plan GUI.

4.3 Application aware In-flight Encryption

As critical infrastructure moves to the cloud, cyber security is becoming an essential service with network encryption as a critical building block in the overall infrastructure. Support for encryption is available at different network layers. However, a diverse suite of protocols, most commonly employed in machine-to-machine communication, have specialized or no support for encryption, complicating the adoption of network encryption. In-flight encryption is a standard mechanism to address this gap by encrypting traffic between trusted sites at the media layer (IP/MAC/PHY). The demand for encrypted service delivery introduces additional complexity, which currently involves the manual translation of high-level requirements by an application into technology-specific configurations for the underlying infrastructure.

This use case demonstrates the capability of ACINO to translate application requirements for in-flight encryption from intents, and based on this and other requirements, identify one or more layers on which to provide encryption.

ADVA has provided a testbed setup, presented in Figure 4.4, which consists of three ROADM nodes interconnected as a ring, with two of the nodes supporting cards with optical encryption capabilities (Annex 5). The setup also includes ADVA FSP 150 series Ethernet switches connected to the WDM ring that can support MACsec encryption, and linux-based hosts running OpenVSwitch instances that can support IPsec encryption.

Figure 4.4: Experimental setup to demonstrate in-flight encryption.

The use case will demonstrate the capability of the ACINO orchestrator to identify the application requirements as pertaining to in-flight encryption, and evaluate trade-offs with other constraints like required throughput and latency. Based on this, ACINO will identify one (or possibly multiple) layers at which to encrypt application traffic and will perform the necessary configurations on the underlying network.

4.4 Virtual CDN (vCDN) adaptation

The vCDN adaptation use case demonstrates the ability to dynamically orchestrate complex workflows in the ACINO architecture based on different application requirements (latency, protection, etc.). In this use case, the application is a user requesting video streaming. The video is assumed to be available at vCDN1 which is a central caching point, and the system will provide the video from an optimal network point based on the requirements of the user.

In the first case, the application requirements (very low latency) indicate that vCDN3 is the optimal point from which to serve content to the user, and the ACINO orchestrator moves the video content from vCDN1 to vCDN3, which has the lower latency to the user. Figure 4.5 shows the first step of the scenario.

Figure 4.5: vCDN transfer to the point with lower latency.

1. The controller creates the optical circuit from ADVA1 to ADVA3 to transfer the CDN data.
2. The controller creates a new IP circuit from Juniper 1 (J1) to Juniper 3 (J3) (directly connected to the vCDN servers).
3. Once the circuit is established, the virtual CDN is transferred from vCDN1 to vCDN3 via the new circuit IP circuit.
4. Finally, User can access to the content from vCDN with low latency

At this point, if there is a failure on the network, the operation of the selection of the optimal CDN point needs to be reconsidered. Consider the scenario presented in the next figure, where the link between the router J3 and vCDN3 goes down.

Figure 4.6: vCDN transfers to vCDN2 the content.

1. The controller determines the next optimal server (vCDN2) and creates a new service in the optical layer (red) to transfer data from vCDN1 to vCDN2 and transfers video content to vCDN2.
2. The controller need to create another service from J2 to J3 to create a data path between vCDN2 and the user.
3. Content is now streamed from vCDN2 to the user.

4.5 In-operation network planning

This use case demonstrates the capability to allocate and optimize IP and optical resources for applications. Application service requests are processed sequentially by the ACINO orchestrator and are accommodated as they arrive. This makes the use case dynamic, i.e. in-operation. The purpose of the use case is to show resource allocation on an empty network, then re-allocation of the already-existing resources, and finally a combination of the two.

As a reference example, we present scenarios to demonstrate the operations involved in this use case. Consider a scenario where applications are characterized by their required bandwidth and latency. In the example, bandwidth is specified as fractions of R , where R is line rate (10 or 40 or 100...Gb/s). Latency is specified as the number of fiber-link hops that the application packets cross. Each application described below will request a connection between node A and node B and all fiber-links can carry only two wavelengths each.

We divide the use case into three phases, where each phase shows a particular interesting action on part of the network.

4.5.1 Initial application-centric resource allocation

We start with the network shown in Figure 4.7. There is one fiber between each pair of nodes, not shown in the figures below. Each fiber can carry only two wavelengths, and there is a wavelength on fiber links (A,C) and (B,C). No application is running on the network yet.

Figure 4.7: Initial network for in-operation planning.

In Figure 4.8, the first request comes from App1, which requires a latency of 1 and a bandwidth of $R/2$. The algorithm will first find that App1 cannot be accommodated in the IP layer because the path (A,C,B) has a latency of 2. As a result, a lightpath using the fiber link between A and B will be used to establish a new IP link to serve the requirements of App1.

Next, App2 arrives, which does not care about latency and requires $R/2$ bandwidth. The algorithm will find a shortest-path in the IP, which is (A,B).

Figure 4.8: a) New IP link established and App1 is accommodated; b) App2 is accommodated in the IP layer.

4.5.2 Moving a connection

We continue with the network from Figure 4.8. App3 arrives and requires a latency of 1 and a bandwidth of $R/2$. The algorithm will first attempt to find an IP path, which fails, because path (A,B) has insufficient bandwidth, and path (A,C,B) has a latency of 2. Next, the algorithm's IP optimization will find that App2 can be moved to path (A,C,B) to accommodate App3 on path (A,B), while App1 cannot be moved due to latency constraints (Figure 4.9).

Figure 4.9: App2 is moved and then App3 is accommodated in the IP.

4.5.3 Establish & move

In Figure 4.10 below, we continue with the network from Figure 4.9. App4 arrives, which does not care about latency and requires R bandwidth. First, the algorithm tries to find an IP path, but this fails because there is no path with remaining capacity R . Next, the algorithm establishes a lightpath on a shortest path in the fiber-link network, which is path (A,B). This lightpath (IP link) can now carry the traffic from App4.

Algorithm details: all possible IP links are first added, which are (A,B), (B,C) and (A,B). Then a lightpath is found on each, so that the lightpaths are shortest. In this case, each lightpath crosses only one fiber-link. On such an IP network, a shortest path is found, which consists of the IP link (A,B).

Next, App5 arrives and requires a latency of 1 and a bandwidth of R . The algorithm first tries to accommodate App3 in the IP layer, and this fails because there is no IP path with remaining capacity R . Next, lightpaths (A,C) and (B,C) are added, and App4, which does not care about latency, is moved to IP path (A,C,B). Then App5 is accommodated on IP path (A,B).

Algorithm details: lightpaths (A,C) and (A,B) are created, but lightpath (A,B) is not because the fiber-links cannot carry three wavelengths. Then IP optimization moves App4, which does not care about latency, to IP path (A,C,B). This frees up IP path (A,B) to accommodate App5, which is done as part of IP optimization.

Figure 4.10: a) a lightpath from A to B is created and then App3 is accommodated in the IP; b) lightpaths (A,C) and (C,B) are created, then App4 is moved to IP path (A,C,B), and finally App5 is accommodated in the IP.

5 Validation of the ACINO Framework

5.1 Scope

These tests will demonstrate the capabilities of the IP and optical controllers, which are required to realize the potential of multi-layer interworking. These capabilities will enable that the ACINO orchestrator can interface with the NBI of multiple SDN controllers for the IP and optical layers, built on an open architecture and emerging standards.

5.2 Lab Tests

The tests will use equipment from one IP vendor and one optical vendor. We will start by basic tests of the functionality of single layer controllers. Note that these tests will not require the current equipment to provide specialized single-layer applications, but to use their current products and implementations. They will either be done via the ACINO orchestrator, or via test scripts talking to the single layer controllers via their own NBI.

5.3 Optical Layer tests

The North Bound Interface of the Optical controller is split in four main functions: (1) Provisioning, (2) Topology Discovery, (3) Monitoring and (4) Path Computation. These requirements generally apply to both DWDM and OTN systems, with the obvious omission of feasibility limitations that only apply to the DWDM layer.

5.3.1 Provisioning tests

Next list presents the tests for the provisioning functions:

- [OP-PROV-1] Set up an unconstrained optical service between two endpoints.
- [OP-PROV-2] Set up an optical service between two endpoints with constraints on the path. Constraints on the path can include:
 - a. Explicit optical path defined by the orchestrator
 - b. Constraints on SRLGs, maximum latency
- [OP-PROV-3] In case a service setup is not successful, the controller must provide appropriate reason codes.
- [OP-PROV-4] Configure a service to employ a restoration/protection path for the current working path (unconstrained).
- [OP-PROV-5] Configure a service to employ a restoration/protection path for a working path, which is itself constrained. Constraints are similar to those employed by the working path.
- [OP-PROV-6] Ability to change the optical restoration path and priority for a connection without requiring a complete re-provisioning of the optical service.

5.3.2 Topology Discovery tests

Next list presents the tests for the topology discovery functions:

- [OP-TD-1] Topology must be able to present Information about the optical nodes with the following information:
 - a. Geo-location information with limited resolution (accurate to the city level)

- b. Type of optical Node and the associated metrics pertaining to performance or restrictions. E.g. in case of amplifiers, gain and OSNR metrics must be provided, and in case of ROADMs, switching constraints (colorless, directionless, contentionless) as well as OSNR and SRLG constraints must be exposed.
- [OP-TD-2] Within the scope of Optical Nodes with Add/Drop capabilities, the topology must expose:
- a. Optical ports / transponders that are currently employed in services
 - b. Spare/Unused transponders that can be used for services
 - c. Special Port attributes that can be configured by the operator and be used to correlate an optical port with a port on an endpoint in another domain (e.g. port on an IP router)
- [OP-TD-3] Topology should provide information about optical services, including routing and wavelength information, as well as additional resources (e.g. regens) that are used by the service.
- [OP-TD-4] Topology should provide information about the fiber links including optical characteristics, span length etc.

5.3.3 Monitoring tests

Next list presents the tests for the monitoring functions:

- [OP-MON-1] Alarms for link failures and equipment failures – both a summary of current alarms, unsolicited messages and location when a new alarm arrives or is cleared.
- [OP-MON-2] Ability to control the administrative states of client side interfaces of a transponder (towards the router) in the optical network. Administrative states supported must include:
- a. Locked (Used in a service, and alarms are forwarded to a management system)
 - b. Unlocked (Client can be used by other services, and no alarms are forwarded to the management system)
 - c. Off (When off, the laser towards the client is not emitting light and no alarms are forwarded to the management systems)
- [OP-MON-3] Ability of a client facing interface to sense and alarm if there is no light received from the router.
- [OP-MON-4] Ability to control the administrative states of services in the optical network. Administrative states supported must include:
- a. Locked (Entities in the service are not usable by other services and alarms are forwarded to a management system)
 - b. Unlocked (Critical alarms from the service components are suppressed, and changes to the service are feasible)
 - c. Off (Lasers are shut down, and no alarms are reported from associated entities)
- [OP-MON-5] Alarms in case optical restoration fails and the reason for the failure.

5.3.4 Path Computation tests

Next list presents the tests for the path computation functions:

- [OP-PCE-1] Path computation for a feasible unconstrained optical path between two end points.
- [OP-PCE-2] Path computation for a constrained feasible path. Constraints can include:
- a. Latency, risk diversity (exclude SRLGs), fate sharing with other paths (include SRLGs)
 - b. Capacity (for systems supporting flexible modulation format), etc.
 - c. Link / Node inclusion or exclusion, and adherence to a loose or strict explicit path
- [OP-PCE-3] The response of a feasible path must include the explicit path, its wavelength, regenerators to be used (if any)

- [OP-PCE-4] Note that the path query can either be for a working path or restoration path, and is subject to the same checks as done during setup (for example, the sharing of restoration resources as a function of diversity of their respective working paths).

5.4 IP Layer tests

The North Bound Interface of the IP controller is split in three main functions: (1) Provisioning, (2) Topology Discovery, and (3) Monitoring. Please note that most of the functionalities described in this section for the tests are expected to be available in both the physical and the emulated setups, and the upcoming deliverables dealing with the evaluation of both scenarios will point out any discrepancies.

5.4.1 Provisioning tests

Next list presents the tests for the provisioning functions of the IP Layer:

- [IP-PROV-1] Set up IP routing path Set up an IP link by defining the salient attributes for the link and the router ports at both ends. An example of a salient attribute is destination subnet.
- [IP-PROV-2] Reallocating IP routing path by defining new salient attributes.
- [IP-PROV-3] Set up IP tunnel by defining the salient attributes and the router ports at both ends. An example of a salient attribute could be the encapsulation type.
- [IP-PROV-4] Reallocating IP tunnels by defining new salient attributes).

5.4.2 Topology Discovery Requirements

Next list presents the tests for the topology discovery functions:

- [IP-TD-1] Discover a set of routers with their features (e.g., names, hardware and software version). This information may be accessible via REST, GUI or CLI.
- [IP-TD-2] Discover a list of ports for each router with their features (e.g., IP Address, status). This information may be accessible via REST, GUI or CLI.
- [IP-TD-3] Discover the adjacencies between routers (e.g., the remote peer for each established connection). This information may be accessible via REST, GUI or CLI.

5.4.3 Monitoring and maintenance tests

Next list presents the tests for the monitoring functions:

- [IP-MON-1] Produce and receive Alarms for port or equipment failure. The event should be propagated to registered applications or recorded in the logging interface.

5.5 Multi-layer Orchestrator

These tests will demonstrate the capability of ACINO Orchestrator to interface with multiple SDN controllers for the IP and optical layers. The South Bound Interface of the orchestrator is split in four main functions: (1) Provisioning, (2) Topology Discovery, (3) Monitoring and (4) Path Computation.

5.5.1 Provisioning

Regarding the provisioning of the services, the orchestrator shall:

- [OR-PRO-1] Provision an IP link by defining the salient attributes (e.g., link bundling properties, encryption).
- [OR-PRO-2] Provision an optical lightpath by defining the salient attributes (e.g., lambdas, encryption) through the NBI.

- [OR-PRO-3] Validate a Service Request. DISMI primitives are recognised, each intent contains only unique connection points, and the connection points are valid.
- [OR-PRO-4] Validate the DISMI Intent compilation. DISMI actions are converted to a proper list of ACI Intents. For each ACI Intent generated: (1) DISMI constraints are converted to equivalent ACI constraints, (2) DISMI selectors are converted to equivalent ACI selectors, and (3) DISMI end points are validated and converted to equivalent ACI end points.

5.5.2 Topology Discovery

The underling network shall be exposed by the orchestrator to provide over the NBI:

- [OR-TD-1] Retrieve detailed list of devices and their ports. This information may be accessible via REST, GUI or CLI.
- [OR-TD-2] Retrieve the links at the IP and Optical layers. This information may be accessible via REST, GUI or CLI.
- [OR-TD-3] Retrieve and store available connection points. This information may be accessible via REST, GUI or CLI.
- [OR-TD-4] Retrieve a service request. This information may be accessible via REST, GUI or CLI.
- [OR-TD-5] Retrieve a detailed list of the low-level provisioned services such as IP routing information and Optical lightpath. This information may be accessible via REST, GUI or CLI.

5.5.3 Monitoring

The orchestrator shall be aware of the current network status that includes:

- [OR-MON-1] Retrieve the status of the ports both at the IP and Optical layers. This information may be accessible via REST, GUI or CLI.
- [OR-MON-2] Retrieve the IP and Optical links status. This information may be accessible via REST, GUI or CLI.
- [OR-MON-3] Retrieve and report the status of network equipment. The event should be propagated to registered applications or recorded in the logging interface.

5.5.4 Path Computation

To allow the interaction with an external Path Computational Element (i.e., Net2Plan), the orchestrator shall:

- [OR-PC-1] Export the topology to Net2Plan representation both for the network topology and the services (e.g., IP routes, optical lightpath).
- [OR-PC-2] Trigger the Net2Plan calculations.
- [OR-PC-3] Allow the submission of Net2Plan demands.

5.5.5 Generic Performance metrics

These tests will also estimate the performance of the Orchestrator when executing key tasks such as: provisioning of network services, topology discovery and service restoration in case of failures. The metric used for the performance evaluation is the time spent by the Orchestrator to complete the process. The measures will be carried out over both the emulated and the physical testbed. Further measurements will be defined on a per use case basis.

- [OR-PERF-1] Establishment of IP/Optical connections.

- a. Measurement: The time it takes to process a DISMI intent and to convert it into vendor-agnostic installable objects (i.e., excluding the latencies due to the vendor-specific translations in the southbound interfaces and excluding the latencies introduced by the control channels and by the network hardware).
- b. Metric: Average time in the order of seconds. Tentatively, less than 5s.

[OR-PERF-2] Topology discovery.

- a. Measurement: The time it takes to discover the topology and to present it to core-layer and application-layer modules. The test will measure the ability of the southbound interfaces to translate the vendor-specific topology descriptions into a vendor-agnostic objects and to make them available for the upper layers in a consistent format. The test will be performed at different sizes of the network (number of nodes and links).
- b. Metric: Average time to discover the topology in the order of seconds. Tentatively, less than 10s.

[OR-PERF-3] Failure recovery.

- a. Measurement. Reconfiguration time necessary to restore a network service after a failure. In this case, the ACINO online planning tool will be compared with the ONOS Intent Framework (used as baseline). The test will consider port and node failures, optical and IP restorations and different network sizes.
- b. Metric. Average time to restore a connection serving an application in the order of seconds. Tentatively, less than 10s.

6 Conclusions

In order to summarize what has been explained in the document, here there is a briefly discuss of each section.

The first section shows us the three preliminary tests as the orchestrator demonstration to show the capability to interact with the physical set-up deployed at Telefonica premises, the restoration on the policy request by the client application and the DISMI demonstration.

The description of the preliminary test-bed with the Data Communication Network to allows us to manage and interconnect the controller and the partners, then, the testbed characteristics and the equipment used.

In the next section, shown the definition of the use case validation, where the differentiated service based on intents is demonstrated, then, the enabling dynamic services, the encrypted application delivery, the vCDN adaptation use case and the in-operation network planning.

Final section presents the controllers validation, where is explained the scope and the function of the functional tests to show the four main functions of the IP and Optical controllers: Provisioning, Topology Discovery, Monitoring and Path Computation. Moreover, the section finishes with the tests of the multi-layer orchestrator covering both the South and North Bound Interface (including DISMI and NetRap).

Annex 1 OpenVPN configuration procedure

This chapter describe the procedure to establish the openvpn tunnels between the Telefonica VM vpnacino and the different partners on the Ubuntu Linux operating system (the client is also available for Windows and MacOS, although the installation procedure on those is slightly different).

We use the OpenVPN client for Ubuntu which is the same executable as the server. So, partners have to install the openvpn package on their client machine(s):

```
sudo apt-get install openvpn
```

Copy the client.conf sample config file to /etc/openvpn/

```
sudo cp /usr/share/doc/openvpn/examples/sample-config-files/client.conf  
/etc/openvpn/
```

The openvpn server is installed in the Telefonica facilities in a virtual machine (vpnacino). Five certificates (one for each partner) and configuration files are generated by the server. These files will be provided by Telefonica to the partners:

```
1./etc/openvpn/ca.crt  
2./etc/openvpn/easy-rsa/keys/client1.crt  
3./etc/openvpn/easy-rsa/keys/client1.key  
4./etc/openvpn/easy-rsa/keys/client2.crt  
5./etc/openvpn/easy-rsa/keys/client2.key  
6./etc/openvpn/easy-rsa/keys/client3.crt  
7./etc/openvpn/easy-rsa/keys/client3.key  
8./etc/openvpn/easy-rsa/keys/client4.crt  
9./etc/openvpn/easy-rsa/keys/client4.key  
10./etc/openvpn/easy-rsa/keys/client5.crt  
11./etc/openvpn/easy-rsa/keys/client5.key
```

Copy the client keys and the certificate of the CA provided by Telefonica to e.g. `/etc/openvpn/` and edit `/etc/openvpn/client.conf` to make sure the following lines are pointing to those files. If you have the files in `/etc/openvpn/` you can omit the path.

```
ca ca.crt
cert client1.crt
key client1.key
```

The partner has to at least specify the OpenVPN server name or IP address and the port 1194 used to pass the traffic. The *TelefonicapublicIP* has to be provided by Telefonica. Make sure the keyword `client` is in the config. That's what enables client mode. There is an example of `client.conf` at the end of this section.

```
client
remote TelefonicapublicIP 1194
```

Now start the OpenVPN client:

```
root@client:/etc/openvpn# /etc/init.d/openvpn start
* Starting virtual private network daemon(s)...
*   Autostarting VPN 'client'           [ OK ]
```

Check if it created a `tun0` interface:

```
root@client:/etc/openvpn# ifconfig tun0
tun0      Link encap:UNSPEC  HWaddr 00-00-00-00-00-00-00-00-00-00-00-00-00-00-00-00-00-00
          inet addr:10.8.0.6  P-t-P:10.8.0.5  Mask:255.255.255.255
          UP POINTOPOINT RUNNING NOARP MULTICAST  MTU:1500  Metric:1
```

Check if you can ping the OpenVPN server:

```

root@client:/etc/openvpn# ping 10.8.0.1

PING 10.8.0.1 (10.8.0.1) 56(84) bytes of data.

64 bytes from 10.8.0.1: icmp_req=1 ttl=64 time=0.920 ms

```

The OpenVPN server always uses the first usable IP address in the client network and only that IP is reachable through ping. E.g. if you configured a /24 for the client network mask, the .1 address will be used. The P-t-P address reported in the ifconfig output above is usually not answering ping requests.

Check out the routes:

```

root@client:/etc/openvpn# netstat -rn

Kernel IP routing table

Destination      Gateway          Genmask         Flags   MSS Window  irtt Iface
10.8.0.5         0.0.0.0         255.255.255.255 UH      0 0        0 tun0
10.8.0.1         10.8.0.5        255.255.255.255 UGH     0 0        0 tun0
192.168.42.0    0.0.0.0         255.255.255.0  U      0 0        0 eth0
0.0.0.0         192.168.42.1   0.0.0.0        UG      0 0        0 eth0

```

The following is an example of the client.conf file

```

#####
# Sample client-side OpenVPN 2.0 config file #
# for connecting to multi-client server.    #
#                                           #
# This configuration can be used by multiple #
# clients, however each client should have  #
# its own cert and key files.              #
#                                           #
# On Windows, you might want to rename this #
# file so it has a .ovpn extension         #

```

```
#####  
  
# Specify that we are a client and that we  
# will be pulling certain config file directives  
# from the server.  
client  
  
# Use the same setting as you are using on  
# the server.  
# On most systems, the VPN will not function  
# unless you partially or fully disable  
# the firewall for the TUN/TAP interface.  
;dev tap  
dev tun  
  
# Windows needs the TAP-Win32 adapter name  
# from the Network Connections panel  
# if you have more than one.  On XP SP2,  
# you may need to disable the firewall  
# for the TAP adapter.  
;dev-node MyTap  
  
# Are we connecting to a TCP or  
# UDP server?  Use the same setting as  
# on the server.  
;proto tcp  
proto udp
```

```
# The hostname/IP and port of the server.
# You can have multiple remote entries
# to load balance between the servers.
remote my-server-1 1194
;remote my-server-2 1194

# Choose a random host from the remote
# list for load-balancing. Otherwise
# try hosts in the order specified.
;remote-random

# Keep trying indefinitely to resolve the
# host name of the OpenVPN server. Very useful
# on machines which are not permanently connected
# to the internet such as laptops.
resolv-retry infinite

# Most clients don't need to bind to
# a specific local port number.
nobind

# Downgrade privileges after initialization (non-Windows only)
;user nobody
;group nobody

# Try to preserve some state across restarts.
```

```
persist-key
persist-tun

# If you are connecting through an
# HTTP proxy to reach the actual OpenVPN
# server, put the proxy server/IP and
# port number here.  See the man page
# if your proxy server requires
# authentication.
;http-proxy-retry # retry on connection failures
;http-proxy [proxy server] [proxy port #]

# Wireless networks often produce a lot
# of duplicate packets.  Set this flag
# to silence duplicate packet warnings.
;mute-replay-warnings

# SSL/TLS parms.
# See the server config file for more
# description.  It's best to use
# a separate .crt/.key file pair
# for each client.  A single ca
# file can be used for all clients.
ca ca.crt
cert client.crt
key client.key
```

```
# Verify server certificate by checking
# that the certificate has the nsCertType
# field set to "server". This is an
# important precaution to protect against
# a potential attack discussed here:
# http://openvpn.net/howto.html#mitm
#
# To use this feature, you will need to generate
# your server certificates with the nsCertType
# field set to "server". The build-key-server
# script in the easy-rsa folder will do this.
;ns-cert-type server

# If a tls-auth key is used on the server
# then every client must also have the key.
;tls-auth ta.key 1

# Select a cryptographic cipher.
# If the cipher option is used on the server
# then you must also specify it here.
;cipher x

# Enable compression on the VPN link.
# Don't enable this unless it is also
# enabled in the server config file.
comp-lzo
```

```
# Set log file verbosity.  
  
verb 3  
  
# Silence repeating messages  
  
;mute 20
```

Annex 2 NAT configuration with IPTables to allow direct access to the internal setup

Once the vpn connection is establish with vpnacino some partners require a direct access to certain VM into the lab.

We use IPTables to set a new NAT rules that allow the partners a direct access to the internal network.

The next command let you know the rules running in the vpnacino:

```
sudo iptables -t nat -L -nv

Chain POSTROUTING (policy ACCEPT 382K packets, 23M bytes)

pkts bytes target prot opt in out source destination
936 50624 SNAT all -- * eth0 10.8.0.0/24 10.95.86.192/28 to:10.95.87.87
359 21220 SNAT all -- * eth0 10.8.0.0/24 10.95.86.0/26 to:10.95.87.87
```

The first rule sets the NAT configuration to reach the ADVA optical equipment from the partner side of the tunnel. To configure this rule we use the following command:

```
iptables -t nat -A POSTROUTING -o eth0 -s 10.8.0.1/24 -d 10.95.86.196/28 -j SNAT --to-source 10.95.87.87
```

The second rule sets the NAT configuration to allow the partner connect directly from his side to the subnetwork 10.95.86.0/26. The controllers used for the setup are located on this subnet: acino controller (10.95.86.53) and the adva-virtual-machine where the ADVA controller is installed (10.95.86.30)

```
iptables -t nat -A POSTROUTING -o eth0 -s 10.8.0.1/24 -d 10.95.86.0/26 -j SNAT --to-source 10.95.87.87
```

Annex 3 Juniper vMX configuration procedure

This chapter describe the procedure to install and configure the Juniper virtual MX. We use vMX to create the virtual topology with 3 Juniper routers over/on a Ubuntu host.

Figure: Scenario set-up for the vMX.

Three vMX are launched on the host machine (phoenix). First of all, we install the prerequisite packages in the host:

```
sudo apt-get upgrade

sudo apt-get install bridge-utils qemu-kvm libvirt-bin python python-
netifaces vnc4server libyaml-dev python-yaml numactl libparted0-dev
libpciaccess-dev libnuma-dev libyajl-dev libxml2-dev libglib2.0-dev
libnl-dev python-pip python-dev libxml2-dev libxslt-dev

sudo reboot
```

And unpacking the files and images:

```
tar xzf vmx-15.1F4.15.tgz
```

At this point we have a directory tree with a structure like this:

```
vmx-15.1F4-3
├── build
├── config
│   ├── samples
│   │   └── ...
│   └── vmx.conf
├── vmx2.conf
├── vmx3.conf
└── vmx-junosdev.conf
```

```

├─ docs
│  ├─ mx86_on_openstack_release_notes.pdf
│  └─ VMX_Release_Notes_Installation_Guide_Beta.pdf
├─ drivers
├─ env
├─ images
│  ├─ jinstall64-vmx-15.1F4.15-domestic.img
│  ├─ jinstall64-vmx-15.1F4.15-domestic.tgz
│  ├─ metadata_usb.img
│  ├─ vFPC-20151203.img
│  └─ vmxhdd.img
├─ scripts
└─ vmx.sh

```

And we have to edit the conf files, and create news files, in order to get the appropriate configuration and connections between the virtual routers. The vmxN.conf, which define the VM parameters, is detailed below:

```

#####
#
#  vmx.conf
#  Config file for vmx on the hypervisor.
#  Uses YAML syntax.
#  Leave a space after ":" to specify the parameter value.
#
#####
---
#Configuration on the host side - management interface, VM images etc.
HOST:
  identifier           : vmx1   # Maximum 4 characters
  host-management-interface : eth0
  routing-engine-image   : "/home/<user>/vmx-15.1F4-
3/images/jinstall64-vmx-15.1F4.15-domestic.img"
  routing-engine-hdd     : "/home/<user>/vmx-15.1F4-
3/images/vmxhdd.img"
  forwarding-engine-image : "/home/<user>/vmx-15.1F4-3/images/vFPC-
20151203.img"
---
#External bridge configuration

```

```
BRIDGES:
  - type : external
    name : br-ext           # Max 10 characters

---

#vRE VM parameters
CONTROL_PLANE:
  vcpus      : 1
  memory-mb  : 2048
  console_port: 8603

  interfaces :
    - type    : static
      ipaddr  : 192.168.100.52
      macaddr : "0A:00:DD:C0:DE:0F"

---

#vPFE VM parameters
FORWARDING_PLANE:
  memory-mb  : 8192
  vcpus      : 3
  console_port: 8604
  device-type : virtio
#   vm_distro : yocto           # Yocto specific

  interfaces :
    - type    : static
      ipaddr  : 192.168.100.53
      macaddr : "0A:00:DD:C0:DE:11"

---

#Interfaces (max 10)
JUNOS_DEVICES:
```

```

- interface          : ge-0/0/0
  mac-address       : "f8:bc:12:34:ef:c4"
  description       : "ge-0/0/0 connects to virbr0"

- interface          : ge-0/0/1
  mac-address       : "a0:36:9f:3b:1c:28"
  description       : "ge-0/0/1 connects to eth0"

- interface          : ge-0/0/2
  mac-address       : "a0:36:9f:3b:2c:28"
  description       : "ge-0/0/2 connects to vmx2"

- interface          : ge-0/0/3
  mac-address       : "a0:36:9f:3b:3c:28"
  description       : "ge-0/0/3 connects to vmx3"

```

We must generate the three conf files, one per virtual router, and change the identifier in order to generate the juniper router and generate the desired topology. To create the links that appear in the topology, we must edit the file `vmx-junosdev.conf`.

```

#####
#
# vmx-junos-dev.conf
# - Config file for junos device bindings.
# - Uses YAML syntax.
# - Leave a space after ":" to specify the parameter.
# - For physical NIC, set the 'type' as 'host_dev'
# - For junos devices, set the 'type' as 'junos_dev'
# and set the mandatory parameter 'vm-name' to
# the name of the vPFE where the device exists
# - For bridge devices, set the 'type' as 'bridge_dev'
#

```

```
#####  
interfaces :  
  
# links to virbr0  
  - link_name : vmx_link  
    mtu       : 1500  
    endpoint_1 :  
      - type      : junos_dev  
        vm_name   : vmx1  
        dev_name  : ge-0/0/0  
    endpoint_2 :  
      - type      : bridge_dev  
        dev_name  : virbr0  
  
  - link_name : vmx_linkb  
    mtu       : 1500  
    endpoint_1 :  
      - type      : junos_dev  
        vm_name   : vmx2  
        dev_name  : ge-0/0/0  
    endpoint_2 :  
      - type      : bridge_dev  
        dev_name  : virbr0  
  
  - link_name : vmx_linkc  
    mtu       : 1500  
    endpoint_1 :  
      - type      : junos_dev  
        vm_name   : vmx3  
        dev_name  : ge-0/0/0  
    endpoint_2 :
```

```
- type      : bridge_dev
  dev_name  : virbr0
# Connections between mvx
- link_name : vmx_link4
  endpoint_1 :
  - type     : junos_dev
    vm_name  : vmx1
    dev_name : ge-0/0/2
  endpoint_2 :
  - type     : junos_dev
    vm_name  : vmx2
    dev_name : ge-0/0/1

- link_name : vmx_link5
  endpoint_1 :
  - type     : junos_dev
    vm_name  : vmx2
    dev_name : ge-0/0/3
  endpoint_2 :
  - type     : junos_dev
    vm_name  : vmx3
    dev_name : ge-0/0/2

- link_name : vmx_link6
  endpoint_1 :
  - type     : junos_dev
    vm_name  : vmx3
    dev_name : ge-0/0/1
  endpoint_2 :
  - type     : junos_dev
    vm_name  : vmx1
```

```
dev_name      : ge-0/0/3
```

Now we have the virtual router correctly configure so we can launch it:

```
./vmx.sh -lv --install --cfg config/vmx.conf
./vmx.sh -lv --install --cfg config/vmx2.conf
...
./vmx.sh -bind-dev
```

The next step is login in a vMX and set the internal IPs to all the interfaces present in junosdev.conf file. We can access to the vmxN with user: root and no password.

```
./vmx.sh -console vcp vmx1
```

Also, after login, we can access to CLI and show the current configuration

```
Login: root
  <no pass>
root@% cli
root> show configuration
```

To set the IP to an interface, we have to enter to configure mode and run set or delete command

```
root> configure
root# set interfaces <ge-0/0/N> unit 0 family inet address
<192.168.122.5/24>
...
root# delete interfaces <ge-0/0/N> unit 0 family inet address
<192.168.122.5/24>
```

The IPs at the end of the same link must belong to the subnet, so the IPs set to ge-0/0/0 must belong to the subnet defined by the virbr0 IP, that is present in host.

This configuration must be set in all the vMX according to the topology scheme. After that we can probe if the different links are correctly configure.

```
vmx1@root> ping 192.168.155.2      #ping to vmx2
vmx2@root> ping 192.168.156.3     #ping to vmx3
```

```
host> ping 192.168.122.3    #ping to vmx3 from host
```

Annex 4 Juniper logical systems configuration procedure

In order to support multiple teams working on the same infrastructure Junos allows using logical-systems. The logical systems partially splits the router so each team can use their part of the router without affecting the other part of the equipment.

```
set logical-systems acino
set system login class acino permissions all
set system login class acino logical-system acino
set system login user acino full-name acino
set system login user acino class acino
set system login class acino permissions all
set system login user acino authentication plain-text-password
```

Annex 5 In-flight encryption with ADVA ConnectGuard

In-flight optical encryption in the ACINO project was demonstrated [5] using the ADVA ConnectGuard solution which can encrypt payloads in an optical channel. As seen in Figure 4.4, the setup for the demonstration uses three ADVA FSP 3000 ROADMs, two of which are equipped with the 5TCE10G AES cards. The encryption setup requires the setup of a shared secret key on the encryption endpoints. The shared secret is used for mutual authentication of the endpoints. Once authenticated, endpoints use an in-band channel and the Diffie-Hellman algorithm to exchange keys used for symmetric encryption, and the payload itself is encrypted using the AES-256 algorithm.

The key differentiating factors in the ConnectGuard solution are its low latency and high throughput. Technologies like IPsec include an authentication header and a CRC hash at the end of each packet. The inclusion of an additional header leads to reduced throughput, especially when packet sizes are small, and the computation of the CRC check on the encrypted payload requires that the buffering of the complete packet (after encryption) to compute the payload. The ConnectGuard solution uses the in-band channel to signal the start of the encrypted payload, and encrypts the complete ODU payload using an FPGA-based implementation of the AES-256 algorithm, which adds negligible delays (~ 100ns) to the transmission process. Finally, the encrypted ODU payload is encapsulated in an OTU2 frame and sent over the optical carrier. By not introducing additional authentication headers and CRC checksums, the ConnectGuard solution provides in-flight encryption with no throughput penalty and a negligible delay penalty.

The in-flight encryption card used in the demonstration is capable of transporting an encrypted ODU2/ODU2E payload, and has the capability to multiplex multiple lower order signals into this payload. For the demonstration, a GbE client interface connected to the router is encapsulated into an ODU payload, which is then encrypted and transmitted over the optical channel.

References

- [1] ICT STRAUSS Project, www.ict-strauss.eu/en/
- [2] M. Santuari, T. Szyrkowiec, M. Chamanía, R. Doriguzzi-Corin, V. López, D. Siracusa, “Policy-based Restoration in IP/Optical Transport Networks”, in IEEE NetSoft Conference and Workshops (NetSoft), June 2016.
- [3] Introduction to Logical Systems, Juniper, https://www.juniper.net/documentation/en_US/junos15.1/topics/concept/logical-systems-overview-solutions.html
- [4] Netphony project, Telefonica, <https://github.com/telefonicaid/netphony-abno/wiki/>
- [5] M. Chamanía, T. Szyrkowiec, M. Santuari, D. Siracusa, A. Autenrieth, V. Lopez, P. Sköldström, S. Junique, “Intent-Based In-flight Service Encryption in Multi-Layer Transport Networks”, in 2017 Optical Fiber Communication Conference (OFC), March 2017.